

The Development of Management Information Systems for Personnel Development Planning at the School of Information and Communication Technology, University of Phayao

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July , 2021</p> <p>Accepted: February , 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Management Information System, Human Resource Development Plan</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6047919</p>	<p><i>The objective of this research is to analyze the design and development of management information system huge of the personal data components in government organizations that are management issues in human resource planning. It has two essential components: The first component is the development of management information system. The second component is the evaluation of management information system. This research is a research and development. There were 21 samples used to evaluate the system. It consists of executives and staff who are involved in the development of the human resource planning. The tool used in this research consists of two parts. The first part is system design and development tools. The second part is the management information system evaluation tools. It consists of the satisfaction questionnaire for management information system. The statistics used in the research were mean and standard deviation. The results showed that 1) the development results of information systems for management can be used as well as: personnel data, self-development history information, academic position request information, personnel development plan information, personnel development report, and performance report according to personnel development plan. 2) User's performance assessment results showed the highest level ($\bar{x}=4.33$). 3) Information system performance results for front management at very high level ($\bar{x}=3.71$). 4) The results of the information system performance assessment for program management are very high ($\bar{x}=4.02$). 5) Management Information System Performance Assessment Results Security is at the highest level ($\bar{x}=4.29$).</i></p>

Introduction

Currently, public and private organizations have adopted management information systems (MIS) to perform various data storage operations within the organization. Whether it's small or large, a university education system that focuses on the use of relevant information within the organization to store data in a pattern will have a system that supports management work to make decisions on increasing the performance of executives and workers, which covers the transmission, conversion, storage, therefore making the processing and search of information of the work system very convenient to manage.

The School of Information and Communication Technology, University of Phayao, divides the management structure according to the types of personnel, which are divided into two categories: academic and support personnel, classifying academic staff into 10 departments, and 4 support units. It shows the diversity and distinction of personnel comprising their age, qualifications, assignments, and so on. For personnel to work effectively and achieve the objectives of the organization. It is necessary to have a personnel storage system, a good operational system, as well as personnel operation planning. For this reason, it is important that managers and HR practitioners focus on being able to use the information that is available to them correctly, according to their needs, and maximum benefit. In addition, presenting information to executives for use in personnel development planning is an important task in personnel management and human resource unit. Because personnel development is a duty that must be always performed in order to increase efficiency for personnel. Having a framework or guidelines for personnel development to have good skills and behavior will help personnel in the organization to perform according to their career goals. There is a timely report on the performance to make the management know the performance of personnel, strengths, weaknesses. Moreover, it is an improvement that must be developed further in the organization.

The researchers came up with the idea of developing an information system for management for personnel development planning at the School of Information Technology and Communications, University of Phayao. Implementing a system to support personnel's performance and to provide information services and

facilitating communications to requesters quickly, can immediately summarize information or report based on demand. Also, it can reduce the operational procedures of individual workers, resulting in more efficient operations, including the use of system information to make decisions for executives in various factions within the agency. More importantly, the use of system information is for supporting personnel development planning to get the most out of its personnel and agencies.

Research Objectives

- 1) To develop the Management Information System for personnel development planning at the School of Information and Communication Technology, the University of Phayao.
- 2) To assess the efficiency of the Management Information Systems for personnel development planning at the School of Information and Communication Technology, the University of Phayao.

Literature Review

Sounthornwiboon and the research team have studied the development of an efficient management system (Sounthornwiboon et al., 2015). They aimed at needs analysis to develop a management information system (MIS) model for sports organizations using a mixed method approach. Data collection tools consisted of group discussions and needs analysis checklist questionnaires. Data were analyzed using percentage, mean, standard deviation, and content analysis. The MIS Sport Model is built on qualitative and quantitative data, with the sample suggesting three levels of management: top-level management; middle management and operational level management. Therefore, it is necessary to develop MIS Sports software and applications to support decision-making at all levels.

Kaewboonma and the research team conducted a research study on solving flood problems in northeastern Thailand (Kaewboonma et al., 2013). They developed a knowledge domain and designed an architecture to create a decision support system (DSS) using a qualitative approach through interviews with 10 experts in environmental engineering, water resources engineering, and GIS specialists that are also involved in the process of developing scope of knowledge, classify and structure knowledge for CRB flood management. The resulting research results are knowledge domain and DSS architecture, knowledge base, knowledge structured by following three phases of the disaster management cycle. It consists of 9 domains of prediction, 10 domains of response, 9 domains of recovery, 16 domains of history, 30 domains of Geoinformatics, and 6 domains of government policy and land use.

Gill & Luckananurung have studied water management with a focus on applying technology to knowledge management services (Gill & Luckananurung, 1992). They are designed to accommodate users without prior training in data processing automation. It can be accessed using a user-friendly dialogue/system. The task is divided into 6 logical steps, each of which is handled by a separate screen, selective retrieval is accomplished through four different methods of defining the area and by action. Based on user-specified constraints to include any database variable, the primary type of output is (1) fetched data file, filters according to user requirements, (2) pre-formatted assortment of reports, (3) calculates geochemical parameters and diagrams, (4) the two-variable distribution diagram and linear regression analysis, (5) the posting of data and calculation results on the map, and (6) the characteristics of the aquifers. The database manager performs real-time data integrity checks. It makes it possible to edit at the time of data entry.

These are examples of the success and importance of implementing information management technologies in organizations. In addition, there are many other relevant research studies (Chandrasapth et al., 2022; Nantasaksiri et al., 2021; Salaisook et al., 2020; Syukur, 2021; Thepwoongsa et al., 2021; Wongkumchai & Kiattisin, 2021; Yodsuban & Nuntaboot, 2021). All of this inspired the researcher to conduct this research.

Research Methodology

Research Tools

It contains two key components of a research tool: 1) Database analysis and design tools include Draw.io for diagrammatic presentations, and Microsoft Power Point for visualizing user interfaces, and Visual Studio Code for system development tools. 2) The tool used to assess the effectiveness of a management information system is a questionnaire consisting of four areas: competence, functionality, application functionality and security requirements.

Targeted Audience

The samples used in the system development were 1) 64 academic personnel of the School of Information and Communication Technology, in University of Phayao, and 2) 23 personnel from the School of Information and Communication Technology, in University of Phayao. Whilst the samples used to assess system performance include those involved in the preparation of personnel development plans and those involved in the

use of information, including the dean, deputy dean, assistant dean, head of the office of the supervisor and course president of 21 people with a specific selection.

Research Process

There are four main components of the research process: 1) The study of composition and data collection for research includes studying personnel data, studying data and self-development history, studying academic position request data, studying performance reporting data according to the personnel development plan, querying and collecting data obtained from elemental studies to analyze and classify the data that you want to use. 2) The second step is the stage of data analysis. It is the analysis of system usage requirements from users by using the information obtained in the study process and collecting data to analyze the work process. 3) The third step is the stage of the design and development. It is the use of the results of the analysis of system requirements to analyze the feasibility by evaluating the current system and how it has weaknesses and strengths in order to design the functionality of the system using Visual Studio Code. Finally, the last step is the stage of the system performance assessment. It is an assessment by experts and people involved in using the system to identify deficiencies in the database to support decision-making and management's planning, as well as to assess satisfaction with the working system in use.

Statistics Applied in Research

These are the mean and standard deviation that were interpreted by using the following criteria:

The mean is 4.21 – 5.00 = The Highest Acceptable.

The mean is 3.41 – 4.20 = High Acceptable.

The mean is 2.61 – 3.40 = Moderate.

The mean is 1.81 – 2.60 = The Low Acceptable.

The mean is 1.00 – 1.80 = The lowest Acceptable.

Research Results

Result from the System Analysis

Results are in the form of analyzing the needs of the system directly from users who need to use information that is accurate and up-to-date in order to facilitate users in the use of information in the implementation of the planning for personnel development. The information that can support executive decision-making and be used for quality assurance is divided into three areas as follows:

1) Demand for personnel information includes personnel history information, contact information, attendance information, packing information, job position information, academic position information, work status information, education information, and number of personnel classified by type of personnel.

2) The need for information and self-improvement history includes training/seminar/view of work, budget usage information, personnel development, leave information, outstanding personnel information.

3) The need to use academic position request information includes evaluation status information. Teaching and documentation used to evaluate the teaching, status information, requests for academic positioning, teaching evaluation information and documents used to evaluate the teaching of teaching materials/teachings, information requesting academic positioning.

Result from the System Development

The researchers used the Visual Studio Code program to develop the system to meet the requirements of the user, consisting of personal information and basic information of personnel, information, self-development of personnel, academic position information, information, personnel development plan, and presented the User Interface Design as follows:

Figure 4 Personnel self-improvement information

Figure 5 Personnel self-improvement information

Figure 4 and Figure 5 shows the information of personnel's self-development that consists of information on the training/seminars/work visits. Information on the use of budget for self-improvement and educational leave can be accessed for all users. Users can access this information which is disclosed and used for internal operations only.

Figure 6 Academic position information

The researchers determined a specific group of assessors by selecting from those involved in the preparation of personnel development plans and those involved in the use of information (agency executives), including the Dean, Deputy Dean, Assistant Dean, Head of the Office, Head of the Unit, and Course President at the School of Information and Communication Technology, with the following details:

Table1The Assessment Results of the User Requirement

List	\bar{X}	SD.	Interpretation
1. The system can search for personal profile information correctly.	4.35	0.49	The Highest Acceptable
2. The system can search for information on study leave correctly.	4.41	0.62	The Highest Acceptable
3. The system can search for teaching evaluation information and requesting academic positions correctly.	4.47	0.51	The Highest Acceptable
4. The system can report the budget used to develop one's own potential according to the personnel development plan correctly.	4.29	0.85	The Highest Acceptable
5. The system can accurately locate the personnel development plan and report the results of the personnel development plan implementation.	4.12	0.70	High Acceptable
In total	4.33	0.64	The Highest Acceptable

From Table 1, the assessment results of the user requirement showed the highest acceptable level ($\bar{x}=4.33$, SD. = 0.64). The highest level of satisfaction in the system can be searched for the highest acceptable level of teaching evaluation and academic position requests ($\bar{x}=4.47$, SD. = 0.51), and the lowest satisfaction in the system can accurately locate the personnel development plan and report the results of the personnel development plan implementation at the high acceptable level ($\bar{x}=4.12$, SD. = 0.70).

Table2The Assessment Results of the Functional System

List	\bar{X}	SD.	Interpretation
1. Accuracy of adding, deleting, editing of users	3.53	0.80	High Acceptable
2. Accuracy of recording and editing personal history data	3.76	0.83	High Acceptable
3. Accuracy of the search for personal history and other data	3.71	0.85	High Acceptable
4. Login authentication is appropriate.	3.82	0.95	High Acceptable
5. Consistency of the actual system	3.71	0.77	High Acceptable
In total	3.71	0.83	High Acceptable

From Table 2, the results of the assessment of the system's functionality were at a very acceptable level ($\bar{x}=3.71$, SD. = 0.83). The highest level of satisfaction with login authentication was highly satisfied ($\bar{x}=3.82$, SD. = 0.95). Whereas the lowest satisfaction was that the accuracy of adding, deleting, editing of users. It has a high level of satisfaction ($\bar{x}=3.53$, SD. = 0.80).

Table3The Assessment Results of the System Utility

List	\bar{X}	SD.	Interpretation
1. The system is suitable, convenient, and easy to use.	3.94	0.75	High Acceptable
2. The system is suitable for selecting letters, sizes, and colors in the display of data.	4.06	0.83	High Acceptable
3. The system is the same standard in image screen design.	4.12	0.60	High Acceptable
4. The system is suitable for positioning components on the monitor.	3.88	0.70	High Acceptable
5. The system can easily query and issue reports and provide accurate information.	4.12	0.60	High Acceptable
In total	4.02	0.70	High Acceptable

From Table 3, it was found that the assessment of the system utility showed that the satisfaction level was at the acceptable level. The highest satisfaction with this topic is that the system is the same standard in image screen design. It has a high acceptable level of satisfaction ($\bar{x}=4.12$, SD. = 0.60). Meanwhile, the lowest

satisfaction with this topic is that the system is suitable for positioning components on the monitor ($\bar{x}=3.88$, SD. = 0.70).

Table 4 The Assessment Results of the System Security

List	\bar{x}	SD.	Interpretation
1. The system can system and assign permission correctly.	4.24	0.56	High Acceptable
2. The different levels of permission are appropriate.	4.35	0.49	High Acceptable
3. System security processes are appropriate.	4.29	0.47	High Acceptable
In total	4.29	0.50	High Acceptable

From Table 4, it was found that the assessment of the system security showed that the satisfaction level was at the high acceptable level. The highest satisfaction with this topic is that the different levels of permission are appropriate. It has a high acceptable level of satisfaction ($\bar{x}=4.35$, SD. = 0.49). Meanwhile, the lowest satisfaction with this topic is that the system can system and assign permission correctly ($\bar{x}=4.24$, SD. = 0.56).

Research Discussion

This study focused on the development of management information systems for personnel development planning of the School of Information and Communication Technology, at University of Phayao. The researcher set up the research process that was divided into the following 4 sections: 1) A study of the composition and collecting data for use in research, 2) Data analysis, 3) Design and development, and 4) Assessment of the system's efficiency by developing an information system that was divided into five areas as follows: 1) personnel information, 2) personnel self-development information, 3) academic position information, 4) personnel development plan information, and 5) personnel performance report which assesses the opinions of the assessor with regards to the information system.

The overall user demand was at the highest level. Assessor's opinion on the functional information system of the overall system is at a high acceptable level. Also, the assessor's idea of the overall safety information system was at the highest acceptable level. It can be concluded that the development of management information systems for personnel development planning is appropriate for implementation.

Furthermore, it can be applied in the management information systems (MIS) which can meet the needs of users, reduce redundancy in the worker's data storage, reduce the problem of data mismatches, and update information that can be accurate at all times. Providing information services and facilitating communication for service applicants quickly, it can bring information to be summarized or reported as needed immediately, and reduce the worker's workflow, thus resulting in actions that are operating more efficiently.

Conclusion

The objective of this research is to analyze the design and development of management information system huge of the personal data components in government organizations that are management issues in human resource planning. It has two essential components: The first component is the development of management information system. The second component is the evaluation of management information system. This research is a research and development. There were 21 samples used to evaluate the system. It consists of executives and staff who are involved in the development of the human resource planning. The tool used in this research consists of two parts. The first part is system design and development tools. The second part is the management information system evaluation tools. It consists of the satisfaction questionnaire for management information system. The statistics used in the research were mean and standard deviation.

The results showed that 1) the development results of information systems for management can be used as well as: personnel data, self-development history information, academic position request information, personnel development plan information, personnel development report, and performance report according to personnel development plan. 2) User's performance assessment results showed the highest level ($\bar{x}=4.33$). 3) Information system performance results for front management at very high level ($\bar{x}=3.71$). 4) The results of the information system performance assessment for program management are very high ($\bar{x}=4.02$). 5) Management Information System Performance Assessment Results Security is at the highest level ($\bar{x}=4.29$).

Recommendations

This research is very useful for coordinating and providing additional information from the staff of the University of Phayao. It facilitates to reduce data entry time and keep data consistent. For the next research, the researcher aims to develop the system to be able to display statistics in graph format, which will be convenient for data analysis and decision making according to various actions. of executives more easily

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